

15 Years of International Nuclear Security Education Network (INSEN): Achievements and a Vision for Tomorrow

Alpana Goel¹, Metwally Walid², Ayoade Kuye³, Mohammed Sallah⁴, Jovana Nikolov⁵, Alexandra Ioannidou⁶

¹Amity Institute of Nuclear Science & Technology, Amity University Uttar Pradesh, Noida 201313

²Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Oak Ridge, TN, USA 37830

³Department of Chemical Engineering University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria

⁴Physics Department, Faculty of Science, Mansoura University, Mansoura 35516, Egypt

⁵University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Trg Dositeja Obradovica 3, 21000, Serbia

⁶School of physics, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece 54124

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ABSTRACT

The International Nuclear Security Education Network (INSEN) was launched in March 2010 under the auspices of the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) to strengthen and sustain nuclear security education worldwide. Over the past 15 years, INSEN has evolved from a small group of academic and policy experts into a global partnership of universities, research institutions, industry, and other stakeholders that collectively develop curricula, teaching materials, faculty training, and outreach initiatives. These efforts have built the foundation for a new generation of nuclear security professionals.

Recent milestones include the maturation of working groups, formalization of curricula guidance, expansion of educational resources, and continued membership growth. In 2025, INSEN marks its fifteenth anniversary with the launch of INSEN for Youth, a flagship initiative to enhance engagement with students and early-career professionals. This paper traces INSEN's evolution, reviews its impacts, highlights challenges and lessons learned, and outlines recommendations for its next phase.

Keywords: INSEN, Milestones, Membership and Global reach and Core functions

1. HOW IT STARTED AND EVOLVED?

The International Nuclear Security Education Network (INSEN) was established at an IAEA workshop in March 2010 [1] by educators, technical officers, and representatives from international organizations and professional associations. The workshop aimed to review existing and future nuclear security academic programs worldwide, share lessons learned, and explore mechanisms to enhance cooperation among institutions.

The absence of an established professional network and a recognized, university-level curriculum that treats nuclear security as a distinct and interdisciplinary field were the primary motivators for INSEN's creation. INSEN's mission was thus focused on the development and implementation of academic programs in nuclear security and the establishment of a collaborative network among universities, research institutes, industries and other stakeholders involved in nuclear security education [2].

The need for structured human resource development programs in nuclear security has been repeatedly emphasized at IAEA General Conferences, Board of Governors meetings, and through successive IAEA Nuclear Security Plans. The current plan, covering the period 2022–2025 [3], gives high priority to assisting States in establishing sustainable educational programs in nuclear security. Ministerial Declarations from 2013, 2016, 2020, and 2024 [4] International Conferences on Nuclear

Security reaffirmed the importance of collaborative networks such as INSEN in achieving these goals.

The IAEA, in cooperation with academic and nuclear security experts from Member States, published IAEA Nuclear Security Series No. 12 – Educational Programme in Nuclear Security (2010) [5], which provided a model for a Master of Science (M.Sc.) and Certificate Program in Nuclear Security. Following practical feedback from INSEN members, the guide was revised and published as IAEA Nuclear Security Series No. 12-T (Rev.1) – Model Academic Curriculum in Nuclear Security in August 2021[6]. All educational materials related to both curricula are accessible to INSEN members through the NUSEC portal.

2. TIMELINE OF KEY MILESTONES (2010–2025)

Table 1 shows the key INSEN milestones from its establishment until now.

Table 1. Timeline of key milestones

Year	Milestone
2010	INSEN established during the IAEA workshop; the founding members defined the mission and scope.
2011–2015	Development of working groups, creation of shared teaching materials, and launch of pilot courses and faculty exchanges.
2016–2019	Consolidation phase: alignment with IAEA guidance, establishment of quality assurance practices, and adoption of model M.Sc. curricula.
2020	Tenth anniversary marked; shift to hybrid/online modalities due to the COVID-19 pandemic.
2021–2024	Expansion of membership and resources; increased student outreach; strengthened links with national nuclear security programs.
2025	Fifteenth anniversary and launch of <i>INSEN for Youth initiative</i> , whereby six young professionals selected to contribute to the 2025 Annual Meeting in Mito, Japan. The youth will be working under the expert mentorship and will participate in several panels.

3. MEMBERSHIP AND GLOBAL REACH

INSEN has experienced sustained growth since its establishment. As of July 2025, the network comprises 214 institutions from 75 Member States and 14 observers, reflecting significant geographic and institutional diversity. Between July 2023 and July 2025, ten new members joined from Cuba, Germany, Hungary, Japan, Malawi, Saudi Arabia, Senegal, Somalia, Togo, and the United States of America, along with one observer institution from South Africa [1]. This expansion underscores INSEN’s success in fostering a truly global platform for educational nuclear security. Figure 1 shows the growth of INSEN membership since its establishment. It is interesting to observe how the growth

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 from 2011 to 2015 aligns with the milestones detailed in the table above.

Figure 1. INSEN membership growth

4. CORE FUNCTIONS AND OUTCOMES

The main function of INSEN is to enhance global nuclear security education and strengthen the capacity of academic institutions to teach and train experts in nuclear security

In simpler terms, INSEN works to build and support education, training, and collaboration in the field of nuclear security — ensuring that future professionals have the knowledge and skills to prevent, detect, and respond to nuclear and radiological threats. Key objectives include:

1. Developing educational materials and curricula in nuclear security.
2. Promoting cooperation among universities, research institutions, and international organizations.
3. Encouraging faculty development and sharing of best teaching practices.
4. Fostering academic programs that sustain nuclear security knowledge globally.

INSEN operates through three main working groups, each with specific areas of focus:

Working Group	Main Function / Focus
Working Group 1 (WG1): Development of Educational Materials	Develops standardized teaching materials, textbooks, case studies, and e-learning resources to support nuclear security courses. Ensures consistency and quality in nuclear security education worldwide.
Working Group 2 (WG2): Faculty Development and Training	Focuses on training and supporting educators—through workshops, seminars, and mentorship programs—to effectively teach nuclear security topics. Builds teaching capacity and expertise in institutions.

Working Group	Main Function / Focus
Working Group 3 (WG3): Promotion of Nuclear Security Education and Sustainability	Works on expanding awareness, promoting collaboration, and ensuring long-term sustainability of nuclear security education programs. Encourages new universities and countries to integrate nuclear security into their curricula.

5. IMPACT AND ACHIEVEMENTS

Over its fifteen years, INSEN has contributed to measurable progress in nuclear security education:

- **Academic Recognition:** Many universities now offer formal nuclear security modules or full programs, improving the professional pipeline. INSEN organizes professional development programs for the train the trainers from time to time as per requirement.
- **Resource Sharing:** Centralized access to peer-reviewed teaching resources has increased the quality and consistency of curricula.
- **Global Reach:** Membership across 75 member states enables even emerging nuclear states to develop indigenous expertise and educational programs.
- **Collaborative Community:** INSEN has cultivated a community that bridges technical, policy, and regulatory dimensions of nuclear security.

6. CHALLENGES AND LESSONS LEARNED

Over its fifteen-year history, INSEN has had plenty of achievements in nuclear security education. However, INSEN continues to face several challenges that provide valuable lessons for future growth and sustainability.

Challenges:

1. **Sustainability of Programs:** Stable funding and faculty retention remain essential for the long-term viability of academic programs. Without consistent resources, even well-established initiatives risk stagnation or discontinuation.
2. **Interdisciplinary Integration:** Combining technical, policy, legal, and social science dimensions within coherent curricula remains complex.
3. **Equitable Access:** Differences in institutional resources across Member States can limit participation, restricting opportunities for nations to develop local expertise and build human capacity.
4. **Keeping Pace with Evolving Threats:** Rapid technological and threat evolution require INSEN to regularly update curricula and teaching methods to ensure relevance and effectiveness.
5. **Global Coordination:** Expanding membership across regions poses coordination challenges, including maintaining quality, harmonizing educational standards, and fostering collaborations among institutions with various capabilities.

Lessons Learned

1. **Collaborative Development Multiplies Impact:** Shared materials and peer review enhance

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quality and accelerate program development.

2. **Faculty Capacity Building Is Essential:** Training and supporting instructors have proven to be among INSEN's most effective strategies for sustaining high-quality education.
3. **Youth Engagement Ensures Sustainability:** Initiatives like INSEN for Youth are key to maintaining long-term interest and nurturing the next generation of nuclear security professionals.
4. **Hybrid Learning Expands Reach:** Lessons from the pandemic demonstrated that online and hybrid delivery can effectively increase participation.

By framing challenges alongside corresponding lessons, INSEN highlights not only the obstacles it faces but the strategies as well that have been proven effective in overcoming them, providing a roadmap for continued growth and meaningful impact in nuclear security education.

7. Ongoing Efforts and Future Outlook

To consolidate its achievements and ensure future sustainability, INSEN should consider the following strategic actions:

1. **Institutionalize INSEN for Youth:** Transform the 2025 initiative into a permanent program offering scholarships, mentorship, and internship opportunities, fostering engagement with students and early career professionals.
2. **Establish Regional Hubs and Micro-Grants:** Support under-resourced members through regional centers for faculty training, lab development, and student fellowships, promoting equitable access and capacity building.
3. **Implement a Curriculum Review Cycle:** Form a standing technical panel to update curricula every 2–3 years in response to emerging threats and technologies.
4. **Develop Impact Metrics:** Introduce standardized indicators—such as graduate placement rates, curricula adoption levels, and gender balance—to assess outcomes.
5. **Strengthening Industry and Practitioner Partnerships:** Expand collaborations with operators, regulators, and security agencies to offer practical training opportunities and ensure that academic programs align with real-world needs.
6. **AI Guidance for Nuclear Security Education:** Sub-group of INSEN members is developing guidance on the use of artificial intelligence in nuclear security education, and the guidance shall be released in 2026.
7. **Empowering gender equality:** Encouraging the participation of girls and women in nuclear security education, enabling them to benefit from the international opportunities, mentorship, and IAEA initiatives, and to contribute to a diverse and inclusive professional community.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Over fifteen years, the International Nuclear Security Education Network has transformed nuclear security education from a collection of isolated courses into a cohesive, collaborative, and globally recognized discipline. Through shared curricula, faculty development, and cross-border cooperation, INSEN has strengthened the foundation of human capacity for nuclear security.

The 2025 launch of INSEN for Youth represents a pivotal step toward engaging the next generation of professionals. By implementing the recommended measures (enhanced youth engagement, regional

capacity building, curriculum renewal, and data-driven evaluation), INSEN can ensure that its first fifteen years of progress become the foundation for a sustainable and globally harmonized future in nuclear security education.

REFERENCES

- [1] IAEA INSEN Web Portal, <https://nusec.iaea.org/portal/User-Groups/INSEN/About-INSEN>. Access date: October 17, 2025.
- [2] International Atomic Energy Agency, IAEA Nuclear Safety and Security Glossary, Interim edition, IAEA, Vienna (2022), <https://www.iaea.org/resources/publications/iaea-nuclear-safety-and-security-glossary>.
- [3] International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). (2022). IAEA Nuclear Security Plan 2022–2025. Vienna: IAEA. Retrieved from <https://www.iaea.org/topics/nuclear-security>
- [4] International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). (2013, 2016, 2020, 2024). Ministerial Declarations of the International Conference on Nuclear Security. Vienna: IAEA. Retrieved from <https://www.iaea.org/topics/nuclear-security/international-conference-on-nuclear-security>
- [5] International Atomic Energy Agency, Educational Programme in Nuclear Security, IAEA Nuclear Security Series No. 12, IAEA, Vienna (2010), <https://www.iaea.org/publications/8363/educational-programme-in-nuclear-security>.
- [6] International Atomic Energy Agency, Model Academic Curriculum in Nuclear Security, IAEA Nuclear Security Series No. 12-T (Rev. 1), IAEA, Vienna (2021), <https://www.iaea.org/publications/13608/model-academic-curriculum-in-nuclear-security>.